

AERODYNAMIC DAMPING MEASUREMENT OF AXIAL COMPRESSOR WITH ACOUSTIC EXCITATION

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, an acoustic excitation system was developed and adopted for damping measurement of an axial compressor. Authors describes the results of damping measurement using an acoustic excitation system under both subsonic and transonic flow fields. Flutter simulation was also conducted by in-house code and compared with experimental results.

In order to obtain sufficient acoustic power to oscillate rotating blade row, acoustic path was adjusted to amplify the sound pressure level. Then, the acoustic excitation system was installed on axial compressor test rig. The frequency response was obtained, and the damping of rotating blade row was evaluated well. In subsonic test, the damping was measured in positive nodal diameter conditions and the measured damping agreed with CFD results. Also, the damping of OND was measured in transonic condition. Finally, the potential of the current acoustic excitation system was evaluated.

Keywords: Aeroelasticity, Aeromechanics, Acoustic Excitation, Unsteady Aerodynamics, Axial compressor, Gas Turbine

NOMENCLATURE

δ	Log. decrement of damping
fb	blade eigenfrequency
$frpm$	rotation frequency
fs	acoustic frequency
m	nodal diameter
IBPA	inter blade phase angle
IGV	inlet guide vane
ND	nodal diameter
R	rotor
S	stator
S_M	sweep rate
TWM	traveling wave mode

1. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the market needs for larger plant output and higher efficiency have increased. In order to meet the continuous demand of the market, Mitsubishi Heavy Industries, Ltd. (MHI) launched the next-generation 1650°C class JAC (J-Air Cooled) series, which incorporates newly developed technology and redesigned components into the existing J-series gas turbine [1]. The JAC series started verification operation at T-point 2 in January 2020, and the final confirmation of the integrity of equipment reliability, performance, etc. has been completed [2,3]. Increasing the inlet mass flow is the most promising way to increase the power output of IGCC plant. In the JAC series compressor, the blade row was re-staggered from J-series compressor to increase mass flow because it was the most robust way [1]. However, it is expected that the cross-sectional area will be increased, and the size of the front stage blade will become longer to realize a further increase of mass flow from the JAC-series. The longer the rotor blade, the lower the stiffness and the higher the relative velocity. As a result, the reduced frequency decreases and flutter becomes one of the important problems.

Aerodynamic damping is the key parameter to determine the stability of vibrating blade rows. Aerodynamic damping can become negative, and it differs from other damping factors such as structural and material damping. Flutter occurs when negative aerodynamic damping exceeds other positive damping of the blade. Therefore, it's important to know aerodynamic damping when the compressor operates.

Several efforts have been made to experimentally measure the aerodynamic damping of rotating blade rows under realistic operating conditions. Meinzer and Seume measured the aerodynamic damping in rotating turbine blade with acoustic excitation. The results showed good accordance with the time linearized CFD simulation [4]. Rey et al used acoustic excitation for active control in flutter [5]. E. Wegman et al developed air

injection system and the system was transferred to the transonic test facility. The air injection system could be used to measure the response characteristics of the blisk [6]. However, the air injection system has relatively large effect on the flow field compared to other excitation methods. Rice et al conducted electromagnet excitation for steam turbine blade model and evaluated the safety margin of flutter [7]. Electromagnet excitation is not an effective method for CFRP or titanium blades because it can't excite nonmagnetic materials.

In this paper, authors adopted an acoustic excitation for damping measurement on axial compressor. Because an acoustic excitation can oscillate the blade row without a large influence on flow field. The other reason is that longer rotor blade might be manufactured by lightweight material such as CFRP or titanium which can't be oscillated by electromagnet excitation. In order to obtain sufficient acoustic power to oscillate the rotating rotor blade, an acoustic excitation system was developed. The acoustic excitation system was installed to axial compressor rig and damping measurement was conducted under both subsonic and transonic condition. The results were introduced, and it compared with CFD results. Finally, the potential of the acoustic excitation system was evaluated.

2. EXPERIMENTAL AND NUMERICAL METHODS

2.1 Acoustic Excitation System

The acoustic excitation system was developed at R&I center of MHI to measure total damping of rotating blade rows. In order to oscillate the rotating rotor blade, it's needed to mount multiple speakers equidistantly over the circumference of rotor. The relationship between the eigenfrequency of the oscillating mode of the blade and the acoustic frequency of speakers in the stationary frame is calculated by Equation (1).

$$f_s = f_b \pm m \times f_{rpm} \quad (1)$$

In this paper, the total damping was estimated from vibration stress measured by strain gauges. From a previous transonic compressor experiment, authors estimated that a sound pressure level of 150dB at the flow path is necessary to obtain a sufficient blade response to measure the total damping.

In the experimental setup, rotor was oscillated by speakers (P-1000, UNI-PEX) installed at eight locations in the circumferential direction (Fig. 1). Since three speakers were mounted in one place, a total of twenty-four speakers were installed on the rotor casing. Considering the blade chord length and target mode, the acoustic path was designed to be 20mm in diameter. The blade row was oscillated from tip of leading edge and the exit of acoustic path was almost perpendicular to the flow path due to space constraints (Fig. 2). The frequency characteristic of a speaker was confirmed in the preliminary test shown in Fig. 3. The sound pressure decreases when the frequency is less than 500 Hz.

The length of the acoustic path was designed to be close to the acoustic resonance point to amplify the sound pressure level. Therefore, two kinds of acoustic paths (path A and B) were

prepared. Path A is suitable for subsonic testing and path B is suitable for transonic testing. The length of them is indicated in Table 1.

The all speakers were controlled by a multi excitation control system for a particular nodal diameter mode to oscillate. Unsteady pressure was measured in each sound path, so the amplitude and phase of the acoustic excitation could be monitored.

FIGURE 1: Speaker placement on compressor rig

FIGURE 2: The cross section of acoustic excitation system

FIGURE 3: Frequency characteristic of speaker (P-1000)

TABLE 1: Acoustic path specifications

	Target	L1 [mm]
Path A	Subsonic test	255
Path B	Transonic test	175

2.2 Transonic Compressor Facility

Geometry of transonic compressor

The acoustic excitation system was installed to transonic compressor test rig. The rig is 1.5 stage compressor, which consists of IGV, 1st rotor and 1st stator. The 1st rotor is titanium blade and has a disk-root configuration. Therefore, there is higher structural damping than blisk. It's not an ideal condition for acoustic excitation, but the condition is sufficient to confirm acoustic excitation potential. CDA (Controlled Diffusion Airfoil) blades were used for all rotors and stators for higher efficiency. Pressure control valves and an emergency valve were installed at the compressor outlet. The former is used to change the outlet back pressure and to move the operating point. The latter valve opens at the moment of surge or flutter.

Based on the design concept described above, the specification of 1.5 stage compressor is shown in Table 2. The rotation speed is 14,400 rpm at design point, and the corrected tip speed is 492 m/s. The Reynolds number was designed to avoid laminar separation of the blade surface. The facility is driven by a 4,000 kW electric motor.

TABLE 2: Specifications of the transonic 1.5 stage compressor rig

Stage	IGV + 1stage
Rotation Speed [rpm]	14,400
Inlet Pressure [kPa]	About 100
Total Pressure Ratio [-]	1.34
Corrected Tip Speed [m/s]	492
Reynolds number [-]	7.5×10^6

Measurement techniques

The overall characteristic was determined by pressure and temperature probes measurements at the inlet (upstream of IGV) and exit of the compressor. Inlet total pressure and temperature were measured using 4 total pressure and temperature probes in the circumferential direction. Outlet total pressure and temperature were measured at the downstream of 1st stator with 4 total pressure and temperature probes in the circumferential direction. Since outlet probes were circumferentially traversable, the overall characteristic considering the wake of stator was obtained. The cross section of transonic compressor facility is shown in Fig.4 and the overview is shown in Fig. 5. The steady wall pressure was also measured upstream and downstream of each blade rows to confirm the stage loading.

In order to evaluate the damping with acoustic excitation, the vibration stress of rotor was measured by strain gauges and telemetric measurement system. The measurement process is shown in Fig. 6. The multi excitation control system produced signals that oscillated a specific nodal diameter mode. The signals were tuned by amplifiers to give same sound pressure to

all speakers. Then, the sound pressure oscillated the rotating blade row and vibration stress was measured by strain gauges. Two strain gauges for each of the four blades were installed. The location of strain gauges was determined by considering the target mode and S/N ratio.

FIGURE 6: Measurement system of acoustic excitation

2.3 Numerical Methods

Governing equations

In-house multi-block three-dimensional compressible viscous Navier-Stokes solver was used in this work. It solves the conservation equations for mass, momentum and energy by a finite volume, second order central difference method. The equations can be expressed in compact form as follows:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \iiint_V \mathbf{u} dV = - \iint_A \mathbf{C} \cdot \mathbf{n} dA + \iint_A \mathbf{D} \cdot \mathbf{n} dA + \iiint_V \mathbf{S} dV \quad (2)$$

$$\mathbf{u} = \begin{bmatrix} \rho \\ \rho U_x \\ \rho U_r \\ \rho r U_\theta \\ \rho E \end{bmatrix} \quad \mathbf{C} = \begin{bmatrix} \rho \mathbf{U} \\ \rho U_x \mathbf{U} + p \mathbf{e}_x \\ \rho U_r \mathbf{U} + p \mathbf{e}_r \\ \rho r U_\theta \mathbf{U} + r p \mathbf{e}_\theta \\ \rho H \mathbf{U} + \Omega r p \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

$$\mathbf{D} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ \tau \mathbf{e}_x \\ \tau \mathbf{e}_r \\ r \tau \mathbf{e}_\theta \\ -q + \mathbf{U} \cdot \boldsymbol{\tau} \end{bmatrix} \quad \mathbf{S} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ p + \rho U_\theta^2 / r \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

Where \mathbf{u} denotes the conserved variables, \mathbf{C} the convective flux terms, \mathbf{D} the diffusive fluxes, \mathbf{S} the source terms and \mathbf{n} are a unit vector normal to the face are dA .

SA 1-equation turbulence model is implemented to model the effects of turbulence [8]:

$$\frac{\partial \hat{v}}{\partial t} + u_j \frac{\partial \hat{v}}{\partial x_j} = c_{b1} \hat{S} \hat{v} + \frac{1}{\sigma} \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \left((v + \hat{v}) \frac{\partial \hat{v}}{\partial x_j} \right) + c_{b2} \frac{\partial \hat{v}}{\partial x_i} \frac{\partial \hat{v}}{\partial x_i} \right] - c_{w1} f_w \left(\frac{\hat{v}}{d} \right)^2 \quad (4)$$

The Reynolds stress is formed based on the Boussinesq assumption where the Reynolds stress is assumed to be proportional to the rate of strain tensor

$$\tau_{ij} = 2\mu_t \left(S_{ij} - \frac{1}{3} \nabla \cdot \mathbf{U} \delta_{ij} \right) \quad (5)$$

Several in-house corrections were conducted to the solver to suppress the generation of turbulence viscosity in the region of the vortex and consider the non-linear effect of strain rate to the Reynolds stress [9]. For details about numerical setup, see [10].

Flutter simulation

The mode shape and frequency used in this study were obtained from a finite element solver and were interpolated onto the CFD grid. The mode shapes remained fixed during computation. The mechanical mode is assumed to be unaffected by aerodynamic forces. This study focused on the first torsional mode (T1), which is shown in Fig. 7. Since Traveling Wave Mode (TWM) analysis was conducted in this study, the rotor blade row was oscillated with the specific mode shape and frequency at various inter blade phase angle (IBPA).

FIGURE 7: Mode shape of first torsional mode (T1)

Computational model and boundary conditions

In this study, two calculation models were used, the entire compressor rig model (Fig. 8) and rotor only model (Fig. 9). The entire compressor rig model contained a strut, inlet guide vane, 1st rotor and 1st stator. The numerical domain was created with a block structured mesh, which was generated using an MHI in-house code. The mesh used for this calculation was a smoothed H-type mesh. Set the mixing planes between rotor and stator. In the rotor only model, inlet and outlet domain were added to the front and rear of the rotor domain. The domains are free slip wall and keep sufficient length to prevent the influence of inlet and outlet boundary to the rotor. In addition, an intentional mesh coarsening in the axial direction, which referred to inflation treatment, was applied to the inlet and outlet domain to avoid pressure wave reflections from entering the calculation model of the interest [11]. The required boundary conditions were obtained from the entire compressor rig model results. As described above, since TWM analysis was carried out, the number of passages was changed according to calculating IBPA conditions.

FIGURE 8: Entire compressor rig model

FIGURE 9: Rotor only model (IBPA ± 90)

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Aerodynamics

In order to evaluate the potential of the acoustic excitation system, acoustic excitation tests were conducted under both subsonic and transonic condition in this paper. Figure 10 shows the operating points of the acoustic excitation tests, and it looks CFD predicts operating point well. Subsonic test was conducted in 50%N* condition. Then, the corrected rotor tip speed is about 246 m/s (OP-1). Transonic test was conducted under 100%N* condition (OP-2). Since the corrected rotor tip speed is about 492 m/s shown in Table 2, it's with shock condition.

Figure 11 shows the radial distribution of the pressure ratio at stator outlet. The measurement results showed good agreement with CFD results. The pressure distribution on 10%Ht of stator is shown in Fig. 12. Good agreement between the measurement and CFD was also obtained. Therefore, the steady calculation results can be accepted as the boundary condition of flutter simulation. Small discrepancies might influence the damping prediction, but this paper doesn't focus on that effect.

FIGURE 10: Operating point of acoustic excitation test

FIGURE 11: The comparison of pressure ratio distribution at stator outlet between CFD and experiment

FIGURE 12: The comparison of pressure distribution on 10%Ht of stator between CFD and experiment

3.2 Structural Dynamics

Frequency mistuning influences flutter stability. Tapping test was conducted in advance to confirm the level of frequency mistuning. In the tapping test, the blade was set in a device having the same root shaped groove and pushed up from the bottom of the blade with a force corresponding to centrifugal force. Natural frequency of 1st torsional mode is shown in Fig. 13. The standard deviation of T1 mode frequency was about 0.7%. The frequency response of tapping test is shown in Fig. 14. From the tapping test, the structural damping of T1 mode was estimated less than 1.0%.

FIGURE 13: Natural frequency of 1st torsional mode

FIGURE 14: The results of tapping test

3.3 Acoustic Excitation Test

Acoustic path influence

Two acoustic paths (path A and B) were prepared to amplify the sound pressure level. Path A is suitable for subsonic testing and path B is suitable for transonic testing. Both paths were applied to subsonic test, and the effect of the acoustic path is described in this section. Two kinds of acoustic paths installed on compressor test rig are shown in Fig. 15.

Figure 16 and 17 shows sound pressure and vibration stress at OP-1 in both path A and path B condition. The target oscillating mode is T1-2ND. The acoustic frequency is calculated from the natural frequency of T1 and Equation (1). Path A, designed for subsonic testing, had a sound pressure about 2.8 times that of path B, and provides a vibration stress 2.4 times that of path B. Since S/N ratio increases as the vibration stress increases, it's suitable for estimating damping. From these results, the sound pressure level can be changed by adjusting the length of sound path, and S/N ratio can be increased.

(a) Path A (b) Path B

FIGURE 15: Two kinds of acoustic path

FIGURE 16: Sound pressure with path A and path B

FIGURE 17: Vibration stress with path A and path B

Subsonic testing

The acoustic excitation test was conducted under subsonic condition, OP-1. The first torsional mode (T1) was focused. Since the compressor rig is disk-root configuration, there is higher structural damping than blisk. Therefore, the measured damping is total damping including mistuning effect, structural damping and so on, and CFD damping means only aerodynamic damping.

The vibration stress was measured with strain gauges. After a Fourier transform, the response was extracted from the spectrum. Moving average was performed to smooth the spectrum. Finally, the resonant peak was picked up, and the damping was estimated by half-power method.

The frequency response of a structure excited by a frequency ramp excitation changes the sweep rate S_M in Hz/s [12]. Sweep rate effect on the measured damping and frequency is shown in Fig. 18. Although the measured frequency variation was less than 1%, the measured damping increased with increasing sweep rate. High sweep rate doesn't have sufficient time to grow the response, so the damping tends to become high, and accuracy decreases. Small sweep rate leads long test time, and continuous excitation at the resonance will damage the blades. Therefore, a sweep rate $S_M = 1.0$ Hz/s was used in this study. It meets the sweep criteria of [12] expressed as Equation (6).

$$S_M < \left(\frac{f_b \delta}{2\pi}\right)^2 \quad (6)$$

(a) measured frequency vs sweep rate

(b) measured damping vs sweep rate

FIGURE 18: Sweep rate effect on measured damping and frequency

Figure 19 shows the experimental data of positive nodal diameters compared with CFD results. The damping was always positive in all nodal diameter. Since the structural damping was estimated to be less than 1.0% from the tapping test, the measured damping was expected to be slightly higher than predicted damping. The measured damping shows good accordance with CFD results except for 8ND. Both experiment and CFD results showed that the maximum damping was at 0ND, and the damping was almost constant more than 4ND. The damping tendency of nodal diameter qualitatively agreed between experiment and CFD.

Figure 20 shows the frequency response of vibration stress under each nodal diameter condition. The response was sufficient to estimate the damping using the acoustic excitation. A moving average was performed for the data, but the frequency response was not clean under the higher nodal diameter condition such as 8ND. In order to measure the damping with sufficient accuracy in high nodal diameter conditions, it is necessary to improve the acoustic excitation system.

Transonic testing

The acoustic excitation test was conducted under transonic condition, OP-2. The first torsional mode (T1) was also focused.

FIGURE 19: Comparison of damping gained from the experiment (sweep rate = 1 Hz/s) and CFD : subsonic test

FIGURE 20: Frequency response of a blade to the acoustic excitation measured by strain gauges (subsonic test)

The experimental data of 0ND compared with CFD is shown in Fig. 21. The aerodynamic damping was always positive in all nodal diameter, and the measured damping at 0ND was almost the same as that of CFD. However, the damping was measured only at 0ND. Since the aerodynamic damping was higher than subsonic flow field, the frequency peak couldn't be clearly defined as shown in Fig. 22.

Potential of current acoustic excitation system

The frequency response was obtained, and the damping of rotating blade row was evaluated using acoustic excitation system in both subsonic and transonic flow condition. Therefore, it is concluded that the acoustic excitation is an effective method to measure the damping of rotating compressor blade rows.

However, this research presents two challenges. First, the frequency response of high nodal diameter condition contains a lot of noise. Since there was no clear frequency peak, the damping accuracy decreases. In order to measure the damping with sufficient accuracy at high nodal diameters, it is necessary to improve the acoustic excitation system. Second, the power of the acoustic excitation system needs to be improved in order to measure higher damping conditions or to oscillate more rigid blade row. In order to verify the accuracy of flutter simulation, more effective tests, such as reducing structural damping by using blisk rotor, are required.

FIGURE 21: Comparison of damping gained from the experiment (sweep rate = 1 Hz/s) and CFD : transonic test

FIGURE 22: Frequency response of a blade to the acoustic excitation measured by strain gauges (transonic test)

4. CONCLUSION

An acoustic excitation system was developed to measure the total damping of rotating blade rows, and the total damping measurements were conducted both subsonic and transonic conditions. The summary is shown as follows:

1. The acoustic excitation system had sufficient power to oscillate blade row in both subsonic and transonic conditions. An acoustic excitation system is suitable for the measurement of aerodynamic damping of nonmagnetic material blades with small effect on the flow field.
2. In order to measure the damping with sufficient accuracy in high nodal diameter conditions, it is necessary to improve the acoustic excitation system. The power of the acoustic excitation system needs to be improved in order to measure higher damping conditions or to oscillate more rigid blade row.
3. In order to verify the accuracy of flutter simulation, more effective tests, such as reducing structural damping by using blisk rotor, are required.

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